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ENHANCING EMPLOYEE AND ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE THROUGH HRD PRACTICES

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Abstract

Objective- Performance is a major multidimensional construct aimed to achieve results and has a strong link to strategic goals of an organization (Mwita, 2000). The aggressive fierce market scenario has created the significance of human resource critical than rest of the resources and thus for enhanced Employee Performance (EP) and superior Organizational Performance (OP), development of Human Resource (HR) is solution positioning the Human Resource Department (HRD) at top. As highlighted by various surveys, Performance Appraisal (PA), Training & Development (TD), Knowledge Management (KM), Employee Engagement, Employee Motivation and other Human Resource Management/ Development (HRM/D) practices which organizations are practicing are resulting into achievement of various Organizational Objectives (OO) like Employee Skill Development, Enhanced Employee Performance, Employee Commitment, etc. leading to superior organizational performance. The objective of this paper is to find out relationship between HRM/D practices like PA, TD and KM with employee and organizational performance.

Design / Methodology/ Approach-The present research paper is relationship establishing effort and is based on various secondary data obtained especially from research papers. The paper studied the paper highlighting the effect of PA, TD and KM on employee and organizational performance.

Findings- This study found that there is positive influence of PA, TD and KM on employee and organizational performance. Benefit is achieved through the combined effort of the three practices and other factors also play role. Overall there is affirmative relationship between PA, TD and KM with enhanced EP and OP separately and collectively.

Limitations- Present study is restricted to three practices only while the influence of other factors is not covered. Study based on primary data would have been better.

Practical implications-The findings of this study will encourage the practicing managers and employers in utilizing the three practices namely PA, TD and KM to enhance employee and organizational performance.

Originality/Value- This content of this paper is based on 123 secondary sources and the findings and conclusions are included in this paper. Categorically, the effect of PA, TD and KM on EP and OP was studied from each paper and the sorted findings are summarized and brought forward.

Key words: Employee/Organizational Performance, Human Resource, Performance Appraisal, Training & Development, Knowledge Management, Human Resource Management/ Development, Organizational Objectives.

1. INTRODUCTION

This study is second in series and is in way of my PhD programme. The first one was with another organizational objective i.e. competitive advantage.

1.1 Purpose of The Study

Indian industry sector is going smooth and substantiating, as per the latest reports. Industries are moving towards positive direction suggests that it is achieving its organizational goals. Human Resource Department, Human resource Management/ Development and Organizational Goal are

the three elements which require discussion to carry on this paper. Following relationship among these elements can be established.

Organizations achieves financial profits and enhanced brand image through various organizational objectives like employee skill development, employee competence, enhanced employee performance, employee commitment, organizational performance, organizational growth etc. There OO are gained by developing HR using various HRM/D tools like performance appraisal, training and development, knowledge management etc. The three HRM/D tools PA, TD and KM have significance task of generating competence in HR as a person and in a group. PA helps training and development by providing required relevant data and later KM provides proper matter and process for the TD. The training and development activities load the individual or group with pertinent managerial, behavioural and technical knowledge, skills, and abilities.

It needs to be checked whether the above mentioned associations actually are so directly present. To verify the relationship, the researcher has studied and analyzed the various research papers. This paper is restricted only to employee performance and organizational performance as OO. The present endeavor of this paper is to set up association between employee performance and organizational performance and few HRM/ D tools applied on HR.

Temple (2002) stated that as the performance of an organization is dependent on the quality of the workforce at all levels of the organization it is essential to discuss the concept of individual performance. [2] Campbell (1999) focused on measurement and defined performance as behavior or action relatedt to the realization of an organization's goals that can be measured. [3] Afshan et al. (2012) defined the performance as the attainment of specific tasks measured against predetermined or identified standards of accuracy, completeness, cost and speed. [4]

Various researchers defined organizational performance differently. Venkatraman and Ramanujam (1986) explained the term organisational performance as a sign of the capacity of a company to efficiently achieve independent goals. [5] Daft (2000) said that organizational performance is the organization's capability to accomplish its goals effectively and efficiently using resources. [6] Richardo and Wade (2001) stated that achieving organizational goals and objectives is known as organizational performance. [7]

1.2 The Hidden Purpose of the Study

Higher education essential purpose is to generate and improve employability skills in graduates. Graduates are not as per the industries' expectation. NASSCOM reports suggest that less than 25 percent of graduates are taken as employable. Recent graduates lack various skills required for the employment, as per recent CareerBuilder India national online survey. [8] The real challenge is un-employability. Industry requirement and higher education yield need to be matched.

If we compare two areas namely industry and education then we find that the process is same but output is different. Talking in terms of HRM/ D, in industry output is quality product or services through the human resource that are developed by the HRD. In case of education institution the output is the human which makes the approach different. The association among the HRD, HR and HRM/ D can be show as follows:

The final purpose of the study is to utilize the finding as foundation for research in educational institutions to set up the relationship mentioned above for educational institutions. The research can be made to see if HRD is present in educational institutions. If it's there then why the advantage of HRD is not seen and if it's not there then how the HRD can be established so that human resource i.e. the teachers can gain.

The main topics are discussed one by one to understand little background of this study.

1.3 Human Resource Management

Human Resource Management (HRM) is an important process for making best possible utilization of human resource to achieve the organization objectives. In organization the problems are more human and social than physical, technical and economical making human resource as most significant. In today's world, to overcome challenges, development of new capabilities is crucial. Bratton (1999) said about that human resource management is to integrate and maintain employee to achieve the purpose and goals of organization. [9] HRM includes the values, policies and practices which lead to performance maximizing maintaining balance the two interests i.e. personal and the economic. Staffing, reward, employee development, maintenance, and relations are the five functional areas of HRM. [10] HRM includes four main elements- acquisition, development, motivation and maintenance of human resources. Human resource planning, recruitment and selection, training and development, performance management, compensation and benefits, labour relations are the major components of HRM.

1.4 Human Resource Development

This Human Resource Development is sub part of Human Resource Management which includes functions like performance/ potential appraisals, training & development, career development, knowledge management, succession planning etc. The term Human Resource Development first time was used by Len Nadler (1970) with unified three-fold notion training, education, and development. [11] HRD is used for assessing, selectively upgrading and appropriately deploying human potentialities for achievement of envisioned goals, which foster human dignity. [11] Werner and DeSimone (2006) defined HR Development as: “ A set of systematic and planned

activities designed by an organization to provide its members with the opportunities to learn necessary skills to meet current and future job demands.” [12]

1.5 Performance Appraisal

Rudrabasavaraj considered performance appraisal as a systematic, orderly, and objective method of evaluating the present and potential usefulness of the employees to the organization. [13] Performance need to be measured in term of work related behavior. Maximizing the performance of firm is the major concern for an organization. Performance are appraised which is “comparing the employee’s present and past performance to his/her performance standards.” [14] PA is a procedure to evaluate how individual personnel are performing and how they can improve their performance and contribute to overall organizational performance. [15] There are good relations between various training and development practices and various measures of firm’s performance. [16]

1.6 Training and Development

Peteraf (1993) defined training and development as the procedure to acquire or transfer knowledge, skills and abilities needed to carry out a specific activity or task. Training and development deliberates on the knowledge, skills and attitudes necessary to achieve organizational goals and also to enhance employee and organizational performance. [17] Training need to be proactive i.e. organization focus is on developing competencies as per the present and future needs. Training anyhow enhances the organization effectiveness. Apospori et al. (2008) found a considerable impact of training on organizational performance. [18] Cooney et al. (2002) considered training which develops a positive orientation on the part of employees towards their work role and the organization and it seems to improve performance by enhancing employee’s skills. [19] Performance appraisal gathers input and suggests the requirement and preparation for training programme.

1.7 Knowledge Management

Knowledge management is a part of training and development involves in acquiring and dissemination of knowledge. Soliman and Spooner (2000) defined knowledge as the ability to sustain the coordinated deployment of assets and capabilities in a way that helps the firm achieve

its goals. [20] Harman and Brelade (2007) defined knowledge management as the acquisition and use of resource to create an environment in which information is accessible to individuals and in which individuals acquire, share, and use that information to develop their own knowledge and are encouraged and enabled to apply their knowledge for the benefit of the organization. [21]

1.8 Employee and Organizational Performance

Performance and job performance is synonyms to EP in whole discussion ahead. Cascio (2006) stated performance as the degree of achievement of the mission at work place that builds up an employee job. [22] Campbell et al. (1993) said that performance is what the organization hires one to do, and do well and further, it is only measurable actions. [23] There are various elements of performance. Mathis and Jackson (2009) stated that performance is associated with quantity of output, quality of output, timeliness of output, presence / attendance on the job, efficiency of the work completed [and] effectiveness of work completed". [24] Cooke (2000) stated that efficiency and effectiveness are ingredients of performance apart from competitiveness and productivity. [25] There are two aspects of performance. Jex (2002) defined a very general level job performance as all the behaviours employees engage in while at work. [26] The performance is having three functional approaches. Milkovich et al. (1991) defined dimensions of job performance in three approaches, as a function of outcomes; as a function of behavior and as a function of personal traits. But personal traits can be omitted. [27] Hersen (2004) stated that defining job performance in terms of outcomes and behavior are easier and more objective than personal traits. [28] Performance is done by HR. Al-Qudah et al. (2014) highlighted that successful organization understands the importance of HR as a critical factor directly affects and contributes on the performance. [29] Employee performance also can be defined as the degree to which employees accomplish work requirements. Kaplan (2003) related EP with employee attributes including characteristics or qualities important to the firm; employee behaviors necessary to complete a job successfully; and employee achievements in terms of specific objectives or aims have been met, exceeded, or not met. [30] The term "performance" includes effectiveness, efficiency, economy, quality, consistency behavior and normative measures.

After having idea about employee performance, it is must to know about organizational performance. Perotti and Javier (2002) argued that organizational performance is equivalent to the famous 3Es: economy, efficiency, and effectiveness, of a certain program or activity. [31] Organizational performance can also be defined as the capacity of an organization to identify and implement the appropriate strategies in the context of the objectives it pursues.

After getting little information of Human Resource Management, Human Resource Development, Performance Appraisal, Training and Development, Knowledge Management, Employee Performance and Organizational Performance, the main elements of this paper, it's needful to discuss once again on the rationale of doing this study.

The present aim this study is to set the connection between use of various Human Resource Management/ Development practices on HR and the Employee Performance and Organizational Performance in Industry while the hidden objective of this paper is to utilize the findings of this study in educational institutions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section discusses about the HRM/ D practices as a whole and then various factors i.e. Performance Appraisal, Training and Development and Knowledge Management which enhances employee performance and organizational performance.

2.1 HRM/ D And Employee & Organizational Performance

HRM/ D practices which includes recruitment and selection, performance appraisal, training and development, compensation, motivation, career and succession planning, promotion etc. plays important role in enhancement of employee as well as organizational performance and the same has been confirmed by many researchers in their papers.

Human is considered to be most important resource. Caliskan (2010) concluded that the way an organization manages its human resources has a significant relationship with the organization's performance. [32] The management of HR should be strategic. Cania (2014) proven that organizations had significantly positively changed their performance through strategic management of human resources. [33] Good HR is always asset for the company. Arshad (2014) believed that by accumulation of human capital and escalating employee motivation,

organizational performance can be augmented. [34] For dealing with this HR, planning and various HRM/ D practices are required. AL-Qudah (2014) found positive relationship between HR planning and organizational performance. [29]

The researchers have concluded that the human resource management/ development practices [29] [35] [36] [37] and specific human resource management-related actions [38] have influence on job performance significantly and measures were found remarkable. [39]

The HR practices benefits the HR in many ways. Katou (2008) advocated that HRM policies directly influence HRM outcomes such as collective skills, attitudes, and behaviours, and thus, indirectly through HRM outcomes improve organisational performance. [40] Researchers supported various factors to be linked with HR practices. Trehan and Sethia (2014) identified that when various factors linked with HR practices, it lead to high level of firm performance. [41] Vermeeren et al. (2008) said that HRM practices lead to enhanced organizational performance when supported by leadership. [42] The researchers highlighted various HRM practices leading to enhanced employee or/ and organizational performance. The recruitment and selection, performance appraisal, training & development, compensation, incentive, promotion, job rotation, employee empowerment, employee participation in decision making, career development/ planning etc. have a positive influence on employee as well as organizational performance. [43] [44] [45] [46] [47] [48] [49] Another important factor verified is motivation of employee. Researchers stated that the employees motivation consequently uplift the performance. [50] [51] [52] Couple of other factors added by other researchers are job design, and supervisory support. [50] Thus, various HRM/ D practices are responsible for enhanced employee and organizational performance.

2.2 PA And Employee & Organizational Performance

Performance appraisal in any organization helps in achieving improved employee and organizational performance. Akinbowale and Lourens (2013) concluded that adequate performance appraisal policy will lead to improved employee performance. [53] Its due to employee involvement, [54] [55] employee participation [56] [57] and the effect will be more when it is interpersonal i.e. between supervisor-subordinate. [53] Few researchers pointed out

motivation as mediating factor. Employee motivation which is result of performance appraisal leads to improved employee performance. [55] [56] [58] [59] [60] [61] Performance appraisal is more effective when employees take it positively. The positive employee's perceptions of performance appraisal [60] as rewarding and by good appraisers [62] have significant impact performance. Researchers also pointed the combination of duo i.e. PA and training. Employees' performance enhancement is the combined outcome of performance appraisal as well as training. [56] [63] [49]

To have more influencing PA approach need to be appropriate. Femi (2013) demonstrated that the adoption of the right performance appraisal technique with fair and transparent approach and development mindset in the organization was found to improve workers performance and commitment. [64] There are other mediating benefits of PA as stated by Iqbal (2013) that the performance appraisal as a strategic approach can be able to improve the competencies, motivation, capabilities and performance of their employees. [61] The PA provides base for training and development of employee.

2.3 TD And Employee & Organizational Performance

The ultimate aim of training and development is to enhance the employee as well as organizational performance through various increased capabilities and competencies. Aguinis and Kraiger (2009) suggested that benefits of training range from individual and team performance to the economic prosperity of a nation and it would be maximized by these factors paying attention to needs assessment, pre-training states of trainees i.e. trainee motivation, training design and delivery, training evaluation, and transfer of training. [65] Even employees also believe that training has its benefits. Ampomah (2016) found that employees link their performance to training which indicate that training and development improve employee performance positively resulting in job satisfaction. [66]

Many researchers (Mohamad et al. 2009, Shaheen et al. 2013, Umar et al. 2013, AL-Qudah et al. 2014, Mohamud 2014, Chaturvedi 2015, Asfaw et al. 2015) confirmed positive relationship between training and development and employee as well as organizational performance. [49] [67] [68] [29] [69] [70] [71]

Organizational performance is reflected by various organizational outputs. The researchers (Jehanzeb and Bashir 2013, Slavic and Berber 2014, Falola et al. 2014 and Olubukunola 2015) concluded that organizations achieve innovations, profitability, efficiency and effectiveness which are the indicators of organizational performance. [72] [73] [74] [75]

Apart from this one of the benefits, which shows the positive organizational performance is productivity. Organizational productivity is achieved through of training and development function (Malaolu and Ogbuabor 2013, Agwu and Ogiriki 2014, Slavic and Berber 2014) [76] [77] [73] There are other pointers of organizational performance achieved by training and development. Training and development also generates organizational competency (Sultana et al. 2012) and teamwork alongwith reduced employee turnover (Obi-Anike and Ekwe 2014). [78] [79]

Categorically there are many mediating outcomes in organizations between training & development and enhanced performance due to training and development function. Tharenou et al. (2007) stated that training is positively related to human resource outcomes and organizational performance. [80] The researchers affirmed (Harel and Tzafrir 1999, Cooke 2000, Cole 2002, April 2010, Ongori and Nzonzo 2011, Malaolu and Ogbuabor 2013, Sethi and Agarwal 2014, Kum et al. 2014, and Singh 2014) that training and development function most importantly enhances skills, knowledge, abilities, competencies, morale, attitude and behavior thus developing employee' efficiency and effectiveness resulting into gain in organizational performance. [81] [82] [83] [84] [85] [76] [86] [87] [88] It also improves drive, initiative, quality of work (Devi and Shaik 2012), hidden talents, motivation and team work which helps in gain organization performance (Gamage and Imbulana 2013). [89] [90] Researchers (Tahir and Yousafzai 2014, Kum et al. 2014 and Nikitha and Madhusudana 2015) highlighted career prospects role by stating that training and development provides better career prospects for employees making them more productive and thus ultimately increased organizational performance. [91] [87] [92]

Through training and development deficiency and gaps are filled. Swart et al. (2005) elaborated that training is a means of dealing with skill deficits and performance gaps as a way of

improving employee performance. [93] Later employee contributes to the OP. Cooke (2000) found that training is a way of increasing organizational performance through increase in individual employee contribution. [25]

Quality training and development is needed for better performance. AL-Sinawi et al. (2015) suggested that employees' service performance is related to their quality training as well as performance appraisal. [63] Awan and Saeed (2014) concluded that designing, developing and deploying excellent training programs generates efficiency, accuracy and effectiveness in employee performance leading to positive organizational performance. [94] Khan (2011) asserted that training and development has positive effect on organizational performance when it is well designed and delivered during the job. [95] Raza (2014) stated that application of strategic training and development makes the employees skilled and their performance get improved leading increase in organizational performance. [96] Good planning and policy play important role. Nassazi (2013) found that training and development with clear policies have an impact on the performance of employees with regards to their jobs. [97] Gordon (1992) affirmed that planned and systematic training results in enhanced level of skill, knowledge and competency that are necessary to perform work effectively. [98] To have effective training output needs of organization must be kept in mind. Elnaga and Imran (2013) suggested that training based on firm specific needs and objectives plays vital role in the building of competencies improving employee performance and organizational productivity. [99] Hafeez and Akbar (2015) found that performance-based training enhance employee performance in different performance & development areas. [100] Training must be continuous and frequent. Quartey (2012) derived that training employees has a positive but moderately strong effect on organizational performance provided it should be frequently and strategically organized. [101] Thus, training and development enhances organizational performance which ultimately leads to gaining of OO. Divyaranjani and Rajasekar (2013) found that training helps employees in enhancing their effectiveness and organizations in achieving their strategic objectives and gives organizations a competitive edge. [102] Niazi (2011) concluded that the strategic positioning of training and development directly promotes organizational business goals and objectives, and thereby enhances organizational performance. [103]

Due to the above mentioned benefits organization must invest on KM. Bartel (1994) found that investment in training boosts employee morale and increases performance. [104]

2.4 KM And Employee & Organizational Performance

Knowledge management although being a part of training and development function but due to today's dynamic and challenging world this area has become very important. Many researchers have confirmed that Knowledge Management practices have strong positive influence on organizational performance as a whole and the two are successful integrated. [105] [106] [107] [108] Alongwith OP there are other benefits of KM. Slavkovic and Babic (2013) divulged that knowledge management has a positive impact on overall organizational performance, process innovation, and administrative innovation. [109]

Knowledge Management includes various elements. Knowledge acquisition, knowledge absorption, knowledge conversion, knowledge storage, knowledge sharing/ transfer with employees i.e. elements of knowledge management affect the intellectual capital and organizational performance in a significantly positive manner. [110] [111] [112]

Out of these elements knowledge sharing is most important. Gholami et al. (2013) concluded that Knowledge Management practices positively and significantly influence the organizational performance especially through knowledge sharing. [113] Knowledge sharing and implicit knowledge revolves around the employee and thus employees are important to stay. Nelson and McCann (2010) affirmed that successful retention of knowledge workers is significantly related to financial performance through strategic knowledge orientation, learning culture orientation, and HR practices. [114]

There are various mediating factors in way from KM to OP. Researchers found organizational learning and innovation as mediating effect of KM while achieving enhanced organizational performance. [115] [116] [117]

Strategy, culture and leadership helps KM. Organizational strategy, organizational culture (Zheng et al. 2009), leadership (Theriou et al. 2011) and organizational learning (Danish 2012) have positive influence in paving path for knowledge management. [118] [119] [120]

The two knowledge management capabilities namely infrastructure and process have significant relationship with organizational performance as stated by Zaied (2012). [121]

Infrastructure includes the technology supporting the knowledge management in anyway. Organizational knowledge management tools supporting sharing of knowledge (Hegazy and Ghorab 2014) and technologies helping employees in mastering their task (Agbim et al. 2013) have positive impact on organizational performance. [122] [123]

So, the knowledge management through its elements and support of technologies focusing more on employees with various mediators and influencers plays important in enhancing organizational performance.

2.5 Review enabled the researcher in developing the following understanding:

2.5.1 The enhanced EP as well as OP is noticeable in industry due to HRM/ D tools but more structured approach is needed.

2.5.2 Correct amalgamation of HRM/ D practices leads to enhanced EP and OP although the amalgamation varies from firm to firm.

2.5.3 Best HRM/ D practices universally accepted is not possible even though lot of research work has been carried out.

2.5.4 HR being the most important resource is now a day treated well and strategically.

2.5.5 The way HR is treated is heart of gaining CA.

2.5.6 Aligning of HRM/ D practices with firm's objectives and strategies is in practice to gain EP and OP.

3. DESIGN/ METHODOLOGY

Research papers available in well-known journals were categorically investigated. Papers focusing on enhanced employee as well as organizational performance due to application of general HRM/ D practices and in specific, of performance appraisal, training and development and knowledge management were thoroughly studied. While studying papers researcher tried to

sort those paper which were showing relationship between or among the HRM/ D practices and EP or/ and OP in any ways. The findings from papers are put in a sequential and systematic manner sustaining the relationship between/ among various HRM/ D practices. This paper is able to reflect the objective of the study satisfactorily.

4. FINDINGS/ RESULTS

An insightful study of present literature aided the researcher to discover most recent facets which are authentic contribution to the body of knowledge. Research shows that Human Resource Management/ Development practices in industry to get enhanced EP and OP has increased and becoming key approach

The major findings of this study are:

- 4.1 Organizations are concentrating on EP as well as OP and striving to gain it.
- 4.2 HRD is gaining more importance due to its role of developing HR.
- 4.3 There is positive relationship between HRM/ D practices and increased EP as well as OP.
- 4.4 There is significant impact of performance appraisal on improved EP as well as OP.
- 4.5 Firms are utilizing training & development as a means for enhanced EP as well as OP.
- 4.6 Organizations are considering knowledge management as separate area to be utilized in gaining enhanced EP as well as OP.
- 4.7 Overall there is affirmative relationship between PA, TD and KM with enhanced EP and OP separately and collectively.

5. OTHER SIGNIFICANT FINDINGS ARE AS UNDER

- 5.1 The motivation of employees has been found most important mediating result of PA, TD and KM on the way to achieve enhanced EP and OP.
- 5.2 On the way in achieving enhanced EP and OP it's the competencies and capabilities developed by combined effort of PA, TD and KM plays its key role.
- 5.3 When HR in organizations are thought to be key element responsible for OP, the better application of HR practices is done. 5.4 Organizations when focus not just on human as resource but the capabilities through HR then better results are achieved in terms of CA.
- 5.5 HRM/ D practices bring CA more when they are If HRM/ D practices are aligned with the organizational goals and strategies then there is more chance of enhanced EP and OP.

6. CONCLUSIONS

As the improved performance of organization is dependent on HR mainly so the enhanced employee performance has taken hot spot in this dynamic world. Organizations are focusing more and more of developing skills, knowledge, abilities, competencies, morale, attitude and behavior of employees in anticipation of enhanced employee performance which ultimately will lead to improved organizational performance. HRD role is becoming more important in this context as the PA, TD and KM can be applied strategically by this department only. The outcome of these HRM/ D practices is enhanced employee as well organizational performance which is one of the organizational objectives. The benefit of PA, TD and KM is more when the same is associated with organization goals and planning. An affirmative impact of PA, TD, and KM separately and in various combinations on enhanced EP as well as OP has been found. TD being in middle depends on KM for the content and process of training and PA provides the need for training and development. Through the application of PA, TD and KM, a mediating factor i.e. motivation plays important role in way to gain enhanced EP as well as OP. In connection to the hidden aim of this study, the application of the above mentioned HRM/ D i.e. PA, TD and KM tools can be verified in educational institutions and by application, enhanced EP as well as OP can be achieved there.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study there is an attempt to find or verify the benefit of HRM/ D practices on enhanced EP as well as OP. The results convincingly can help the HR practitioners in various fields in considering the utilization of HRM/ D practices in obtaining enhanced EP and OP.

7.1 Employees performance is key instrument to organizational performance.

7.2 HRM/ D practices must be focused on developing employees' skills, knowledge, abilities, competencies, morale, attitude and behavior.

7.3 Human resource department must be there in organization updating and working continuously to achieve enhanced EP and OP.

7.4 HRM/ D practices need to be around firms' goals and strategies.

7.5 PA, TD and KM should be practiced together in attempt to gain enhanced EP and OP.

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